

NEUROBIOLOGY

THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN VITAMIN B DEFICIENCY AND COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENT AMONG ELDERLY PATIENTS WITH ALZHEIMER'S AND VASCULAR DEMENTIA

Valkova M.
MD, PhD

University Hospital "Sofamed", Sofia, Bulgaria

Abstract

Vitamin B 12 deficiency (VitB12def.) is frequent among elderly patients. The aim of our study was to examine the effect of Vit.B12def. on cognitive decline among patients with cognitive impairment due to Alzheimer's disease (AD), small vessels disease (SVD) and mixed (vascular and Alzheimer's) dementia (MD).

Material and methods: We examined 49 patients with Vit.B12def. (on average age of 77.76 ± 6.41 years, 18 males and 31 females, 17 with AD, 13 with SVD and 19 with MD) and 97 patients with normal Vit.B12 levels (on average age of 76.07 ± 7.97 , 28 males and 66 females, 21 with AD, 43 with SVD and 33 with MD) twice (with interval of 2 years) via Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), Isaac's Set Test (IST), Literal fluency Test (LFT), Clock Drawing Test (CDT), 10 Words, Digit Symbol Substitution test (DSST 90sec), Digit Span Test (DST forward and backward) and 21 Hamilton Depression Scale. All results were interpreted at 95% confidential level.

Results: Regression analysis showed not linear but square root associations between Vit.B12 level and recognition. CDT, DST forward and DSST, exponential correlations between Vit.B12 and recognition at the second examination and reciprocal correlation with IST at the second examination.

Conclusions: Vit.B12def. is with high prevalence among elderly with AD, SVD and MD. It might lead to additional domain specific cognitive decline (executive functioning, hippocampal memory and visual-special abilities). The association between the levels of Vit.B12 and cognitive performances is non-linear, mostly square root. Patients with such dementias should be examined for Vit.B12def. and should be adequately treated.

Keywords: cognitive impairment, Vitamin B 12 deficiency, Alzheimer's disease, small vessel disease, mixed dementia.

Introduction:

Vitamin B 12 deficiency (VitB12 def.) is frequent among elderly and it is associated with reversible cognitive impairments and dementia (5). Recent studies suggest direct association between VitB12def. and increased risk for developing Alzheimer's disease (7,8), although others question such causality (4). VitB12def. leads to increase of serum homocysteine, which also might cause some cognitive impairments (7). It is also associated with small vessel disease (9).

Vitamin B12 is powerful antioxidant, that cleans super-oxide from mitochondria and cytoplasm and is protective agent from oxidative stress, induced by different factors including methionine, homocysteine and inflammation (7,10). It is of essential importance for cellular energetic processes, myelination and synthesis of brain neurotransmitters (3,7). It also plays important role in the synthesis of fats and nucleic acids and participates in synaptogenesis and nerve cell metabolism (7). Vit.B12def. leads to increased deposition of beta amyloid at the specific brain areas in mice models (7). Animal models also show that Vitamin B12 decreases amyloid proteotoxicity (6) and inhibits alpha-beta fibrillation and deposition of amyloid into amyloid plaques (2).

The aim of our study was to examine the effect of Vit.B12def. on cognitive decline among patients with cognitive impairment due to Alzheimer's disease (AD), small vessels disease (SVD) and mixed (vascular and Alzheimer's) dementia (MD).

Material and methods: Patients with Vit.B12def. showed poor results on recognition, CDT, DST forward and DSST.

We examined 49 patients with Vit.B12def. (on average age of 77.76 ± 6.41 years, 18 males and 31 females, 17 with AD, 13 with SVD and 19 with MD) and 97 patients with normal Vit.B12 levels (on average age of 76.07 ± 7.97 , 28 males and 66 females, 21 with AD, 43 with SVD and 33 with MD). The inclusion criteria of the study were 1. Age ≥ 60 years; 2. Confirmed by neuropsychologist cognitive impairment at ≥ 2 cognitive domains; 3. Confirmed on the basis of history, neurological and somatic examination, laboratory data and imaging study diagnosis of AD or SVD or MD; 4. All patients with Vit.B12def. were treated with Vitamin B12 orally or with muscular injections; 5. No additional causes for anemia of any kind; 6. Lack of other neurological diseases such as trauma, brain tumors, neuroinfections, demyelinating diseases or epilepsy; 7. Lack of decompensation of coexisted somatic diseases during the study; 8. Lack of psychiatric diseases, except of mild depression or anxiety; 9. Lack of treatment or usage of benzodiazepines, modafinile acetate, hallucinogens and other psychoactive drugs, except for low dosages of Quetiapine ($\leq 50\text{mg/d}$), Pregabalin ($\leq 150\text{mg/d}$), Gabaneural ($\leq 600\text{mg/d}$), Hydroxyzine ($\leq 25\text{mg/d}$) or antidepressants; 10. Lack of alcohol abuse or usage of forbidden substances; 11. Signed informed consent.

After clinical interview and confirmation of the diagnosis, the patients were examined via the following neuropsychological battery: Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), Isaac's Set Test (IST for verbal fluency), Literal fluency Test (LFT; variant M-O-H-A in Bulgarian, 1 minute for every letter), Clock Drawing

Test (CDT), 10 Words Test (for working memory, delayed recall and recognition (10/20words), Bulgarian variant), Digit Symbol Substitution test (DSST 90sec), Digit Span Test (DST forward and backward) and 21 Hamilton Depression Scale (HDS). All patients with HDS above 12 points were excluded.

The same neuropsychological battery was used 2 years after the first examination.

The statistical analysis was done via parametric and non-parametric tests as ANOVA, MANOVA, Man-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis test statistics and simple regression analysis via SPSS 20.0 and Statgraphics 20.0. All results were interpreted at 95% confidential level ($p < 0.05$).

Results:

1. Demographics and laboratory data

We presented the demographic data of our patients at table 1. 34% of our patients had Vit.B12def. Patients with and without Vit.B12def. were at similar age and had similar formal education and the groups could be compared. However, we found that Vit.B12 deficiency was more frequent at men than women.

2. The association between Vit.B12def. and cognitive functioning.

We failed to find statistical significant difference on MMSE, short term memory, delayed recall, IST, LFT and DST backward between patients with and without Vit.B12def. ($p > 0.05$). Patients with Vit.B12def. showed poor results on recognition, CDT, DST forward and DSST, although we failed to find additional decline on these scales during the period of the study (see table 2).

The data from the regression analysis was summarized at table 3. We failed to find any association between Vit.B12 levels and MMSE, LFT, 10WT (except for recognition) and DST backward ($p > 0.05$). Regression analysis showed not linear but square root associations between Vit.B12 level and recognition. CDT, DST forward and DSST, exponential correlations between Vit.B12 and recognition at the second examination and reciprocal correlation with IST at the second examination (see table 3).

Discussion:

Vit.B12def is relatively frequent among our patients. More than 1/3 of them had such deficiency. According to Allen et al. (2009) the prevalence of Vit.B12def. among elderly is more than 20%, but in some countries it is up to 40%, more often among people with marginal status. Patients with Vit.B12def.

show poorer performance on scales, that measure attention, hippocampal memory (recognition) and visual-spatial abilities. It is suggested that Vit.B12def. is associated with executive dysfunctions and memory decline, although authors obtain different domain specific cognitive changes (11,12). Such changes remain constant and don't improve with therapy, which suggested constant fronto-temporo-subcortical dysfunction, associated with Vit.B12deficiency, as also suggested other authors (9,11,12). Other cognitive impairments improve over time with the application of specific therapy (5). Because of the high prevalence of Vit.B12def. and its potential role for additional cognitive decline, we suggest that every elderly patient with AD, SVD or MD should be additionally examined for Vit.B12def. and should be adequately treated.

The regression analysis shows non linear model of correlation between the level of Vit.B12 and cognitive impairments (speed of informational processing, recognition, visual-spatial abilities and attention). However, during the period of the study we haven't found any additional decline on examined scales. We should note that all patients with Vit.B12def. were treated with oral or muscular Vit.B12. The correlation coefficients obtained were low. Although these facts, we might say that Vit.B12 deficiency is associated with constant fronto-subcortical changes and hippocampal dysfunction. It may not play role for individual global cognitive functioning but can change his quality of life and decision making and might play important role for the velocity of cognitive decline in elderly. However, according to our data treatment with Vit.B12 in these cases might prevent from additional cognitive decline, associated with Vit.B12def.

Limitations of the study: We examined a relatively small sample of patients for a relatively short period of time. Moreover, all our patients with Vit.B12def. were adequately treated so we don't have untreated control subjects because of ethical and medical purposes.

Conclusions: Vit.B12def. is with high prevalence among elderly with AD, SVD and MD. It might lead to additional domain specific cognitive decline (executive functioning, hippocampal memory and visual-special abilities). The association between the levels of Vit.B12 and cognitive performances is non-linear, mostly square root. Patients with such dementias should be examined for Vit.B12def. and should be adequately treated.

Table 1.

Demographic and laboratory data								
	AD	SVD	MD	Total	Age (years)	M:F	Education B:M:H	Vit.B12(pmol/l)
Patients with normal levels of Vitamin B12	21	43	33	97	76.07±7.97	28:66	9:53:32	277.55±61.97 (Med 234.5)
Patients with Vit.B12def.	17	13	19	49	77.76±6.41	18:31	3:29:17	109.02±47.07 (Med. 101.0)
P=					>0.05	0.0038	>0.05	0.0001
Total	38	56	52	146	76.71±7.47	48:98	12:83:51	202.65±50.06
Legend: AD – Alzheimer's disease, SVD – small vessels disease; MD – mixed dementia; M:F- male:female ratio; Education B:M:H – patients with basic, with middle and with high formal education								

Table 2.

Associations between Vit.B12def. and cognitive performances.

	Averages or medians of patients without Vit.B12def. vs with Vit.B12def.	p=
Recognition 1 (w.)	17.00±2.26 vs 15.94±3.24	0.0251
Recognition 2 (w.)	15.87±3.10 vs 14.58±3.87	0.0331
Decline of recognition (w.)	NA	>0.05
CDT 1 (errors)	0.0 vs 1.0	0.0203*
CDT 2 (errors)	1.0 vs 2.0	0.0144
Increase of the total number of errors on CDT	NA	>0.05
DST forward 1 (p.)	NA	>0.05
DST forward 2 (p.)	5.73±1.58 vs 5.11±1.57	0.0314
Decline of DST forwards (p.)	NA	>0.05
DSST 1 (p.)	30.05±12.76 vs 24.55±13.93	0.0256
DSST 2 (p.)	25.5 vs 17.0	0.0369*
Decline of DSST (p.)	NA	>0.05
Legend: CDT – Clock drawing Test; DST – Digit Span Test; DSST – Digit Symbol Substitution Test		

Table 3.

Regression analysis on the influence of serum Vit.B12 level on cognitive functioning.

The impact of absolute level of Vit.B12 (pmol/l; x) on y:	rr; model	p=
IST1 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
IST2 (p.)	0.17; reciprocal	p=0.0465
Decline of IST (p.)	NA	p>0.05
Recognition 1 (w.)	-0.19; square root	p=0.0223
Recognition 2 (w.)	-0.19; exponential	p=0.0272
Decline of recognition (w.)	NA	p>0.05
CDT 1 (errors)	0.20; square root	p=0.0185
CDT 2 (errors)	NA	p>0.05
Increasing of errors on CDT.	NA	p>0.05
DST forward 1 (p.)	NA	p>0.05
DST forward 2 (p.)	-0.18; square root	p=0.0308
Decline of DST forward (p.)	NA	p>0.05
DSST 1 (p.)	-0.22; square root	p=0.0109
DSST 2 (p.)	-0.21; square root	p=0.0158
Decline of DSST (p.)	NA	p>0.05
Legend: IST – Isaac's Set Test, CDT – Clock Drawing Test, DST – Digit Span Test; DSST – Digit Symbol Substitution Test. rr – correlation coefficient		

References

1. Allen LH. How common is vitamin B-12 deficiency? *Am J Clin Nutr.* 2009 Feb;89(2):693S-6S.
2. Andrade S, Loureiro JA, Pereira MC. Vitamin B12 Inhibits A β Fibrillation and Disaggregates Preformed Fibrils in the Presence of Synthetic Neuronal Membranes. *ACS Chem Neurosci.* 2021 Jul 7;12(13):2491-2502
3. Calderon-Ospina C.A., Nava-Mesa M.O. B vitamins in the nervous system: Current knowledge of the biochemical modes of action and synergies of thiamine, pyridoxine, and cobalamin. *CNS Neurosci. Ther.* 2020;26:5–13.
4. Gagliano Taliun SA. Genetic determinants of low vitamin B12 levels in Alzheimer's disease risk. *Alzheimers Dement (Amst).* 2019 Jun 6;11:430-434.
5. Jatoi S, Hafeez A, Riaz SU, Ali A, Ghauri MI, Zehra M. Low Vitamin B12 Levels: An Underestimated Cause Of Minimal Cognitive Impairment And Dementia. *Cureus.* 2020 Feb 13;12(2):e6976.
6. Lam AB, Kervin K, Tanis JE. Vitamin B12 impacts amyloid beta-induced proteotoxicity by regulating the methionine/S-adenosylmethionine cycle. *Cell Rep.* 2021 Sep 28;36(13):109753.
7. Lauer AA, Grimm HS, Apel B, Golobrodzka N, Kruse L, Ratanski E, Schulten N, Schwarze L, Slawik T, Sperlich S, Vohla A, Grimm MOW. Mechanistic Link between Vitamin B12 and Alzheimer's Disease. *Biomolecules.* 2022 Jan 14;12(1):129.
8. Shrestha L, Shrestha B, Gautam K, Khadka S, Mahara Rawal N. Plasma Vitamin B-12 Levels and Risk of Alzheimer's Disease: A Case-Control Study. *Gerontol Geriatr Med.* 2022 Feb 7;8:23337214211057715.
9. Soh Y, Lee DH, Won CW. Association between Vitamin B12 levels and cognitive function in the elderly Korean population. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2020 Jul 24;99(30):e21371.
10. van de Lagemaat EE, de Groot LCPGM, van den Heuvel EGHM. Vitamin B12 in Relation to Oxidative Stress: A Systematic Review. *Nutrients.* 2019 Feb 25;11(2):482.
11. Ueno A, Hamano T, Enomoto S, Shirafuji N, Nagata M, Kimura H, Ikawa M, Yamamura O, Yamana D, Ito T, Kimura Y, Kuriyama M, Nakamoto Y. Influences of Vitamin B12 Supplementation on Cognition and Homocysteine in Patients with Vitamin B12 Deficiency and Cognitive Impairment. *Nutrients.* 2022 Apr 2;14(7):1494.
12. Zhou L, Song X, Wang J, Tan Y, Yang Q. Effects of vitamin B12 deficiency on risk and outcome of ischemic stroke. *Clin Biochem.* 2023 Aug;118:110591